

Nation Building through Man-Making: The Revolutionary Works of Eknath Ranade Ji

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Abstract:

Many talented people have been born on this earth who perceived their nation through their own unique vision and strove to give direction to their country and the world accordingly. One such hero was Eknath Ranade Ji. Eknath Ranade Ji was a person of versatile talent and profound foresight. He deeply assimilated the thoughts of Swami Vivekananda into his life and to implement them first established the ‘Vivekananda Rock Memorial’ in Kanyakumari. Thereafter, to give concrete shape to Swamiji's principles, he founded ‘Vivekananda Kendra— a spiritually oriented service mission’. Currently, Vivekananda Kendra operates its service projects across nearabout 24 states and 2 union territories of India. It is setting new benchmarks of development through various service programs, social and cultural development initiatives and educational activities thereby fulfilling the dreams of Swami Vivekananda and Eknath Ranade Ji. Through this article, the researcher has attempted to present the great vision and thoughts of Eknath Ranade Ji to everyone.

Keywords: *Vivekananda Rock Memorial, Vivekananda Kendra, Eknath Ranade Ji.*

Eknath Ranade Ji- A Visionary Personality- Achievements and Vivekananda Kendra:

Born on Margashirsha Shukla Tritiya, Vikram Samvat 1971 (November 19, 1914) in Timtala village, Amravati district, Maharashtra, Eknath Ranade was a great social reformer, skilled organizer and far-sighted visionary. He deeply internalized Swami Vivekananda's ideas and resolved to implement them practically. Ranade Ji believed that national resurgence was possible only by putting Swami Ji's teachings into action. Swami Vivekananda emphasized Advaita Vedanta, arguing that India's decline stemmed not from religion, but from ignorance of it. In his view, national education was essential to dispel this ignorance, eliminate misconceptions, and place the nation above all. In *Our Education*, he wrote: “The entire

education system is completely divorced from Indian culture and tradition. A country cannot be called living where its children are ignorant of their culture and take no pride in it. If we lack knowledge of our culture, what will we take pride in?" (Mishra, 2011). Inspired by these ideas, Ranade Ji first established the '**Vivekananda Rock Memorial**' in Kanyakumari. The struggles of this project taught him that a mere stone monument was insufficient to embody Swami Ji's vision. Dedicated workers were needed who could internalize these ideas and propagate them for nation-building. Thus, on January 7, 1972, he formally announced the establishment of 'Vivekananda Kendra: A Spiritually Oriented Service Mission'. From August 1973, five-year training for 16 life-vowed trainees (including two sisters) began at sunrise on the Rock, concluding in April 1974 with deployments across the country. Starting in Arunachal and Assam, the Kendra now operates in 24 states and 2 union territories. Beyond education, it runs nutritious Anganwadi's, youth inspiration camps, rural libraries, medical services, cultural classes, yoga training camps, and spiritual retreats to foster continuous national progress. While the Kendra realized Swami Ji's dream of 'national resurgence,' his vision of 'nation-building through man-making' required schools. Ranade Ji launched a chain of residential and general schools in Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Nagaland, Andaman-Nicobar, and beyond, giving concrete form to Swami Ji's educational ideals. For its contributions to education and rural development, the Government of India awarded the Kendra the 2015 Gandhi Peace Prize on January 16, 2019. The one crore rupees prize money was donated to families of soldiers martyred in the Pulwama attack (Source: khabar.ndtv.com). The list of service projects operated by Vivekananda Kendra Kanyakumari is as follows:

(A) In the field of education:

1. Under Arunachal Pradesh Trust: 36 Vivekananda Kendra Vidyalayas in Arunachal Pradesh.
2. Under Vivekananda Kendra Shiksha Prasar Vibhag Assam: 34 schools in Nagaland, Andaman, Karnataka, and Chhattisgarh.
3. Under Vivekananda Kendra Vidyalaya Trust: 3 schools in Tamil Nadu.
4. Anandalay: Approximately 200 Anandalayas to support school auxiliary activities for children of tea plantation workers in Arunachal Pradesh and Assam, and primary children in Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, and Maharashtra.

5. Balwadi: Approximately 195 balwadis for pre-primary students in Tamil Nadu, Arunachal Pradesh, and Odisha.

(B) Health services:

1. Vivekananda Kendra Numaligarh Refinery Limited Hospital, Numaligarh, Assam.
2. Jogen Basumatary Memorial Vivekananda Kendra Hospital, Suklai, Assam.
3. Vivekananda Kendra Oman Refinery Limited Hospital, Bina, Madhya Pradesh.
4. Indian Oil Corporation Limited Vivekananda Kendra Hospital, Paradip, Odisha.
5. Under Vivekananda Kendra Rural Development Program: 15 medical dispensaries in Tamil Nadu; mobile medical van in Arunachal Pradesh.

(C) Service schemes for rural and tribal welfare and skill development:

1. Vivekananda Kendra Rural Welfare Project, Khatkhati, Assam.
2. Vivekananda Kendra Rural Development Program, Tamil Nadu.
3. Vivekananda Kendra Training and Service Project, Pimplad, Nashik.
4. Vivekananda Kendra Odisha Service Project, Keonjhar and Amlipani, Odisha.
5. Vivekananda Kendra Arunjyoti, Arunachal Pradesh.
6. Vocational training centers for women in Soijosa, Wakro, and Wakko (Arunachal Pradesh); Thoothukudi (Tamilnadu); Boinggaon (Assam); Pimplad, Nashik (Maharashtra).
7. Vivekananda Kendra Natural Resource Development Project, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu.
8. Green Rameshwaram Project, Rameshwaram, Tamil Nadu.

(D) Publication service schemes:

1. Vivekananda Kendra Prakashan Trust, Chennai (English, Tamil).
2. Vivekananda Kendra Hindi Prakashan Vibhag, Jodhpur.
3. Vivekananda Kendra Gujarati Prakashan Vibhag, Ahmedabad.
4. Vivekananda Kendra Assamese Prakashan Vibhag, Guwahati.
5. Vivekananda Kendra Marathi Prakashan Vibhag, Pune.
6. Vivekananda Kendra Telugu Prakashan Vibhag, Hyderabad.
7. Vivekananda Kendra Punjabi Prakashan Vibhag, Jalandhar.
8. Vivekananda Kendra Kannada Prakashan Vibhag, Mysore.
9. Vivekananda Kendra Odia Prakashan Vibhag, Bhubaneswar.

10. Vivekananda Kendra Bengali Prakashan Vibhag, Kolkata.
11. Magazines: Yuva Bharati (English), Kendra Bharati (Hindi), Vivek Vichar (Marathi), Vivek Vani (Tamil), Vishwa Bhanu (Malayalam), Vivek Jagruti (English, Assamese), Vivek Sudha (Gujarati).
12. Vivekananda Kendra Patrika – English thematic magazine every 6 months.

(E) Training institutions for human excellence:

1. Vivekananda Kendra Pratishtan, Kanyakumari.
2. Vivekananda Kendra Ramakrishna Ashram, Nagdandi, Jammu & Kashmir.
3. Vivekananda Kendra Kaushalam, Hyderabad.
4. Vivekananda Kendra Institute for Excellence in Training, Solapur, Maharashtra.

(F) Institutions for civilizational and inter-civilizational cultural studies and research:

1. Vivekananda International Foundation, Chanakyapuri, New Delhi.
2. Vivekananda Kendra Vedic Vision Institute, Kodungallur, Kerala.
3. Vivekananda Kendra Culture Institute, Guwahati, Assam.
4. Academy for Indian Culture, Yoga, and Management by Vivekananda Kendra, Bhubaneswar, Odisha.

(G) Regular institutional activities through branch centers (daily/weekly):

1. Samskar Varg – To instill values and patriotism in the younger generation.
2. Svadhyaya Varg – To expand and sharpen knowledge.
3. Yoga Varg – For practicing yoga in daily life.
4. Kendra Varg – For Vivekananda Kendra workers.

(H) Periodic activities and events:

1. Guru Purnima (Ashadha Purnima).
2. World Brotherhood Day (September 11 – Day of Swami Vivekananda's famous Chicago speech).
3. Sadhana Day (November 19 – Birth anniversary of Hon. Eknath Ji, founder and guide of Vivekananda Kendra activities).
4. Gita Jayanti (Margashirsha Shukla Ekadashi).
5. Samarth Bharat Parva and Swami Vivekananda Jayanti (December 25 to January 12- every year).

6. Yoga Sessions (Training in asanas, pranayama, and Omkara meditation: theory and practice).
7. Svadhyaya competitions with one-day camps for school and college students.
8. Residential training camps for youth and workers.
9. Residential spiritual and yoga education camps.
10. Interactive dialogue sessions on various topics for different sections of society.
11. Sale of books related to Indian culture and Swami Vivekananda's life and ideas.

(I) Memorials and exhibitions:

1. Vivekananda Rock Memorial.
2. Ramayana Darshanam - Bharat Mata Sadanam.
3. Utho-Jago Exhibition (Arise-Awake Exhibition).
4. Gangotri Exhibition.
5. Gramodaya Park Exhibition.
6. Wandering Monk Exhibition

Objectives of Vivekananda Kendra:

Every action plan has some underlying objectives. Eknath Ji also had specific objectives when establishing Vivekananda Kendra. The Kendra's workers are certainly advancing these objectives today. Eknath Ranade Ji did not write down or explicitly state the objectives of Vivekananda Kendra at one place. Rather, these objectives were determined from quotations in his speeches and lectures delivered across various places. Today, activities are conducted accordingly. "The objective of this movement is briefly presented from quotations given by the Kendra's General Secretary Shri Eknath Ranade while addressing public meetings in various cities of the country" (Bhide & Paranjape, 2015). The objectives of Vivekananda Kendra can be summarized and sequenced as follows:

1. Our national nature: Aspiration for liberation.
2. The current contradictory situation.
3. The root disease: Distorted notion of religion.
4. Characteristics of pure religious sentiment.
5. Swami Ji's call: Worship that Lord who is manifest all around us.
6. Two-pronged movement: The demand of the times.

7. The sowing of this movement's seeds happened 75 years ago.

Thus, with these principal objectives established by Eknath Ranade Ji, Vivekananda Kendra continues to march steadily toward progress.

Vivekananda Rock Memorial:

The Swami Vivekananda Memorial built in Kanyakumari is a unique symbol of unity and purity, as well as the aspirations of the entire nation. It represents the beauty and unity of Indian architecture, as the whole country desired its construction, contributed labour, and gave support. This is a memorial whose original conception came from RSS volunteers, blessed by the Ramakrishna Mission. All spiritual, cultural, and national institutions provided full support. All state governments and the central government extended financial assistance. Just as Kanyakumari is the confluence of three seas, this memorial has become a central focal point. In his Bengaluru speech, Eknath Ji said about this Kanyakumari memorial: *“This is a unique symbol of unity and purity in its own way. My faith and belief is that this great memorial manifesting on this sacred site will, in the coming days, unleash such a powerful current of Swami Ji's ideas that the entire nation will be flooded by it. This powerful flow will unite all the excellences present in our nation, culture, and people, infuse new vitality into our national life, and transform this nation into a suitable and effective instrument to play an invaluable role in world welfare”* (Bhide & Paranjape, 2015).

Conclusion:

Swami Vivekananda envisioned a nation where all people are educated, civilized, cultured, and live in a discrimination-free society. Such a society can only be realized through education where every form of learning and practice aims at man-making. To achieve this, humans must be connected and united with one another. For this, India's people themselves must come forward. Swami Ji entrusted this responsibility to the educated community. He said, *“Reading and writing does not mean merely benefiting oneself; after becoming educated, one must work for the welfare of humanity. He had witnessed the poverty of India's people with his own eyes. He wanted educated and affluent people to serve the poor and downtrodden, strive to uplift them, and engage in social service. By social service, he did not mean mere pity or charity; he meant helping in the upliftment of the downtrodden they would rise on their own. He wanted to create a team of such social servants through education”* (Lal, 2011). Eknath Ji's

thoughts aligned perfectly with Swami Ji's. The primary objective behind establishing this Kendra was to spark a nationwide movement that would inspire youth and motivate them to work for the nation's resurgence. Ranade Ji proved that with dedication and clear vision, a person can accomplish in a short time what might otherwise take centuries. Vivekananda Kendra's core objectives are linked to national education, social consciousness, and cultural development. The Kendra aims to provide education that makes individuals self-reliant and awakens national pride within them. To realize these objectives, after years of foundational work, Eknath Ji formally established Vivekananda Kendra on January 7, 1972. Through Eknath Ranade Ji, Swami Vivekananda's grand dream is coming to fruition. The Vivekananda Kendra established by Eknath Ranade is a significant initiative toward nation-building. This article demonstrates how one individual's foresight and dedication transformed Swami Vivekananda's ideas into an organized and enduring movement. The Kendra continues to work with the same enthusiasm and dedication, inspiring India's youth and making substantial contributions to the nation's holistic progress.

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